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Research Article

The Use Of Azolla Pinnata In Veterinary Nutrition: A Case Study Of Nashik, India

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ABSTRACT

Azolla pinnata has been used for centuries in Southeast Asia as a fertilizer in rice production. A new perspective of the plant as a veterinary nutrition was taken into consideration. Azolla pinnata is a small fern with a triangular frond measuring up to 2.5 centimeters in length which floats on the water. The plant Azolla pinnata was collected from rural area of the Nashik. It was dried under a shade for 2-3 days. The size reduction was carried out. Further nutritions were added to the dried powder of Azolla pinnata. By using wet granulation method granules were prepared. The prepared granules were feed to animals like, Cow, Goat, Hen and fishes. The result was observed an increase in production of milk in Cow and goat whereas weight in Hen and fishes.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, the changes in the life style, nature of work and food habits increases the incidents of serious diseases like coronary heart diseases, obesity and diabetes. Phytogenic feed additives have gained increased interest in animal feed to avoid the residual effects of synthetic drugs. This situation apparently demands for the search for medicinally active as well as

nutritionally rich and cheap non-conventional feed resources. Feeds of plant origin, as the green plants are recognized as excellent sources of protein, fat and pharmacologically active secondary metabolites. Recent study reveals that the aquatic plants are good sources of primary and secondary metabolites. Aquatic plants are gaining much interest in food and biomedical research, resulting from its broad range of uses such as human food,

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animal feed and bio-fertilizers. Azolla is a free floating fresh water fern belonging to the family Azollaceae and order Pteridophyta. It is a common bio fertilizer in rice crop. It grows in association with the blue-green. Anabaena azollae, is considered to be the most promising because of the

ease of cultivation, high productivity and good nutritive value.

SUB HEADING:

Exploring Azolla Pinnata: A Nutritional Solution in Veterinary Care – A Case Study from Nashik, India

FIGURES:WORKING PRINCIPLE

TABLE

Name of animals	Initial Production	7 Days	15 Days	21 Days	30 Days
Cow (for milk)	1 lit	1.2 lit	1.4 lit	1.6 lit	1.8 lit
Goat (for milk)	0.5 lit	0.5 lit	0.53 lit	0.55 lit	1 lit
Hen (for weight)	1.5 kg	1.7 kg	1.9 kg	2.2 kg	2.5 kg

CONCLUSION:

It concludes that feeding prepared of A pinnata granules for cow, hen, fish, goat shows increasing production of milk in cow, goat, weight of hen & fish & it indicates that nutrition content in cow, hen, fish & goat.

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RESULT:

The result was observed an increase in production of milk in Cow and goat whereas weight in Hen and fish

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